

Temple at Tell Afis

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During the Iron Age, the acropolis of Tell Afis, a site in north-west inner Syria which had been inhabited since the Chalcolithic period, seems to have progressively been reserved for ceremonial buildings, at the expense of residential units. The excavations carried out by the Italian archaeological mission directed by Stefania Mazzone have brought to light several architectural structures, different in plan, date and functions, of which the best known has been labelled the AI temple. It is a 38/32 x 28 m building, comprising three rooms (vestibule, a central hall, and a rear room) on the longitudinal axis and additional rooms along the sides. The AI temple was preceded, on the same spot, by an older building, of which, however, only a few remains remain. The hypothesis that these remains belong to a previous temple is suggested by the fact that, in an even earlier phase, dating back to Iron Age I, the same area had been occupied by two buildings, whose nature as shrines is indicated by structural elements as well as by some of the materials found within them, such as the remains of some kernoi (cultic vessels that seem to have been in a particular connection to the figure of the weather-god), and remains of birds in abnormal concentration. These Iron Age I buildings, which were built on top of each other, seem to be separated by a short period of time. The available data do not allow to identify the deities or deities that were worshipped in these shrines. Given the continuity of the cultic use for this area, however, it is possible that in Iron Age I there was worshipped the same deity as that of the later phases. According to an Aramaic inscription, almost certainly from Tell Afis, an important temple, and probably the main sanctuary of the city of Hazrak (the ancient name of the site) was dedicated to the god Ilwer. It is therefore possible that also in the previous phases it was Ilwer who represented the main deity worshipped here. The morphology of Ilwer is not well defined, but he seems to be akin to the figure of the weather-god. It is also possible, however, that Ilwer was not the only deity worshipped in his own temple. It is possible, for instance, that some anatomical votives recovered from the area may point to ritual activities related to the sphere of healing and are perhaps a clue of popular devotion rather than official religion. On the other hand, under Assyrian rule the holder of the temple may have been changed, or official cults related to the ruler may have been introduced (for example, that of the god Sin).

Date Range: 1100 BCE - 600 BCE

Region: The Temple at Tell Afis

Region tags: Syria, Levant

The Temple at Tell Afis

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: S. Mazzoni, Tell Afis in the Iron Age: The Temple on the Acropolis: Near Eastern Archaeology 77 (2014), pp. 44-52
- Source 2: S. Mazzoni, Temples at Tell 'Āfiṣ in Iron Age I-III, in J. Kamlah (ed.), Temple Building and Temple Cult. Architecture and Cultic Paraphernalia of Temples in the Levant (2.-1. Mill. B.C.E.). Proceedings of a Conference on the Occasion of the 50th Anniversary of the Institute of Biblical Archaeology at the University of Tübingen (28-30 May 2010), Abhandlungen des Deutschen Palästina-Vereins, 41, Wiesbaden 2012, pp. 23-40
- Source 3: S. Mazzoni, Iron I Temples at Tell Afis, in F. Briquel Chatonnet, E. Capet, E. Gubel, C. Roche-Hawley (eds), Nuit de pleine lune sur Amurru. Mélanges offerts à Leila Badre, Paris 2019, pp. 307-321

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.tellafis.com>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1972-2010

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Tell Afis Archaeological Mission

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

Type of elevation

- Other [specify]: Tell

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Mound

– Leveling of ground

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

A group of structures:

– Yes

|

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No
- ↳ A group of features:
 - No
- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Sacrificial
- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
- ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Collapsed
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes
- ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Probably Ilwer

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1000

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Zakkur stela, which carried a relief, probably stood once in the temple

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: It is unclear who was the figure represented on the fragmentary stele of king Zakkur, which most probably once stood inside the temple

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Clay funnels

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It might have been present, but interpretation of data is uncertain

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: It is probable that the Aramaic inscription of king Zakkur (KAI 202) stood actually in the temple

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Stefania Mazzoni. S. Mazzoni, Tell Afis in the Iron Age: The Temple on the Acropolis. Near Eastern Archaeology, 77(2014)